

PREDICTION OF THE TIME DEPENDENT STRENGTH EVOLUTION OF POLYMER BASED COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

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SUMMARY: Due to the viscoelastic nature of polymers, composite systems such as polymer matrix composites and adhesively bonded joints, exhibit time dependent properties. For reliable applications in constructions it is necessary to have some prediction models and methods in order to take into account, at the design moment, the time dependent variations of the thermo-mechanical properties of such polymer based material systems.

If some models based on irreversible thermodynamics exist for the analysis of the time dependent stiffness characteristics, such as the Schapery nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive equations, completed, if necessary, by some viscoplastic model, there are no predictive models available for the evolution of the strength characteristics.

For a complete durability analysis, for the prediction of the life time and the analysis of the residual structural integrity after an imposed time period we need a basis for the evaluation of the strength variations.

This time dependent strength behaviour can be analysed in an analogous way as the stiffness behaviour, by some empirical extrapolations of the strength parameters in a limit criterium or on the basis of some damage development with specific damage potentials.

The ultimate strength will be obtained when the homogenised stiffness behaviour shows some localisation effects indicating a weakest link zone where rupture will be initiated. It is possible to use some optical methods such as the Electronic Stress Pattern Interferometry (ESPI) in order to identify those localisation zones and to monitor a predictive model for the time dependent strength evolution.

Examples of weakest link identification in a graphite epoxy test specimen by the use of the ESPI will be presented. The identification of the weakest link is obtained by the optical observation of the heterogeneisation of the strain field.

From the analysis of the strength variations it is possible to arrive at admissible stress levels in order to guarantee a safe residual structural integrity for an imposed life time.

KEYWORDS: polymer matrix composites, durability, viscoelasticity, viscoplasticity, damage, residual strength

INTRODUCTION

When we have to design a structural component on the basis of a time-dependent system, such as a polymer matrix composite, we need not only the instantaneous hygrothermomechanical properties, but also some reliable predictions of the evolution of those properties over the imposed life time period under the estimated loading history and changes of environmental conditions. This problem was tackled by a large number of research groups over the last 25 years. We have to mention some of the basic methodologies :

- the micro-macromodel proposed by C. Chamis, [1];
- the generalisation of the time-temperature superposition principle as proposed by H.F. Brinson et al., [2-3-4];
- a method based on the analysis of the failure mode and the identification of “critical” elements proposed by K. Reifsnider et al., [5-6-7];

- a direct damage analysis as developed by R.Talreja, [8-9], P. Ladevèze [10-11] and Y.J. Weitsman [12-13].

We have also to mention a large number of results obtained by the research group of the Kanazawa Institute of Technology under the direction of Y. Miyano, [14-15-16], and the recent general reference work by K. Reifsnider and S. Case, [17]. For a complete durability analysis different loading conditions have to be considered and a large number of papers discussed the fatigue behaviour of composite systems and the related life predictions. We mention here explicitly only the works of B.Harris, [18], F.K. Gamstedt, [19] and G. Caprino et al., [20], but during many international conferences on fatigue behaviour over the last decades special attention was given to composites.

Our research axis is related to the development and extension of the methodology proposed by H.F.Brinson, including the work of C.C. Hiel [21], H.R. Brouwer [22], X. Xiao [23], Y. Qin [24] and P.J.P. Bouquet, [25]. We have also to mention the results of cooperations with the composite research group of Antonio Torres-Marques (University of Porto), e.g. R. Miranda-Guedes [26], and with the composite research group of G. Papanicolaou (University of Patras), e.g. G. Papanicolaou and S.Zaoutsos, [27].

A nonlinear viscoelastic-viscoplastic model is able to predict the stiffness evolution. In order to arrive at the life time prediction and/or an estimation of damage tolerance and residual structural integrity we need also a reliable prediction of the strength evolution or damage development.

CHARACTERISTIC TEST SPECIMEN AND METHOD OF ANALYSIS

A composite material system is a structured continuum made of different materials in interaction. The interaction levels between fibres and matrix in a lamina, and between the lamina in a laminate are not easy to be measured. A direct measure on the real full scale composite is practically impossible but we can use a mixed numerical-experimental method after introducing in a lamina model or a laminate theory the imperfect interface conditions proposed by J. Achenbach and H. Zhu, [28], and developed by Z. Hashin, [29].

Even if it would be possible to obtain the properties of the fibres and the bulk resin we have to assume some level of interaction between matrix and fibres in order to compute the characteristics of the composite lamina. The same has to be applied for the properties of the laminates. Knowing that the interaction between fibres and resin, or between lamina, will be strongly influenced by the curing process we have chosen to start from the unidirectional reinforced lamina as basic test specimen for the measure of the instantaneous characteristics and the prediction of the time and temperature dependent evolution of those properties with a control on a two layer laminate.

The unidirectional lamina, or laminate, is strongly anisotropic in constitutive behaviour changing from elasto-plastic in the fibre direction to viscoelastic-viscoplastic in the transverse direction. The basic test laminate under loading conditions in the fibre direction and different off-axis directions for a number of environmental conditions is used to predict the long term stiffness evolutions starting from short term test results using different accelerating factors.

For our stiffness predictions we have applied the method introduced by H. Brinson, [2], generalisation of the time-temperature superposition principle, valid for simple thermorheological materials, including the temperature but also the stress level, or some stress related invariant, as accelerating factor. For higher stress levels the viscoelastic behaviour becomes nonlinear and for the analysis we have to use the single integral nonlinear viscoelastic constitutive equations developed by R. Schapery, [30]. On the basis of the observed residual strains after creep recovery a viscoplastic correction has to be introduced in the prediction scheme as proposed by Y. Qin, [24]. Such corrections were also introduced by M.Tuttle et al., [31], and discussed by X. Xiao et al., [32]. The prediction of the evolution of the properties of the characteristic test specimen under quasi static loading conditions alone, including biaxial stress states, is not sufficient for more general applications. It is necessary to consider the fatigue behaviour and the interactions between loading modes.

NONLINEAR VISCOELASTIC-VISCOPLASTIC ANALYSIS

The Schapery equations are derived from the Clausius-Duhem inequality and may be written in general form as :

$$n_a = \left(-\frac{\partial G_R}{\partial F_a} \right) + \frac{\partial \hat{F}_q}{\partial F_a} \int_{\psi'}^{\psi} \Delta S_{qr} (\psi - \psi') \frac{d[\hat{F}_r / a_G]}{d\psi'} d\psi'; \quad (1)$$

n_a are the general coordinates e.g. components of the strain tensor, F_a are the generalised forces associated to the generalised coordinates, \hat{F}_q are the interior forces, G is the Gibbs energy, ΔS_{qr} is the transition compliance expressed as :

$$\sum_p \frac{d_{ps}^r d_{pq}^s}{d_p} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\psi - \psi'}{r_p}} \right),$$

$$d\psi = \frac{dt}{a_\sigma} \text{ is the reduced time, } a_\sigma: \text{ shift factor} = \frac{a_D}{a_G}.$$

For a biaxial stress state a reduced expression for (1) was derived by H.R. Brouwer, [22]. For the one-dimensional situation (1) reduces to :

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 S_0 \sigma(t) + g_1 \int_{\psi'}^{\psi} \Delta S \frac{d[g_2 \sigma(\psi')]}{d\psi'}. \quad (2)$$

g_0, g_1, g_2 and a_σ are “nonlinearising” functions. If they are equal to 1, equation (2) reduces to the classical linear constitutive equation for non-ageing viscoelastic solids.

g_i and a_σ are functions of the temperature, other environmental conditions and the stress state.

The prediction of the long term stiffness evolution starting from short term creep and creep recovery results using equation (2) was successfully applied by M. Tuttle et al., [33], by C.C. Hiel, [21] and by X.Xiao, [34], for different graphite reinforced polymer composites with thermoset and thermoplastic matrices. By successful we mean that we can handle the creep and creep recovery experimental data by a master curve treatment. In the master curve procedure curve fitting was initially used and this can lead to growing cumulative errors. Q.Yin, [24] has shown that curve fitting can be replaced by the application of a neural network approach.

A limited part of the creep and creep recovery results for different stress levels are used as “learning” elements for the neural network-based fuzzy inference system (NNFIS) as discussed by Y.Qin et al., [35]. Applied to a specific graphite-epoxy system (Fibredux, Hexcel, 920C-TS-5-42) the obtained predictions were in excellent agreement with the “long” term experimental results. The behaviour of a 4-parameter Burgers model under creep and creep recovery, shows a residual strain related to the flow occurring during the creep period. If we observe residual strains not corresponding to the creep time period we have to consider some pure plastic behaviour.

Such plastic component of the behaviour for different polymer composites was observed and discussed by M. Tuttle et al., [31], by X. Xiao et al., [32] and by Y. Qin et al., [35].

The viscoplastic part of the observed behaviour can be modelled by a Zapas-Crissman functional :

$$\varepsilon_{VP} = \Phi \left\{ \int g_3 [\sigma(t)] dt \right\}. \quad (3)$$

On the basis of a specific expression for (3) :

$$\sigma_{VP}(t) = C \sigma^{Nm} t^m, \quad (4)$$

we obtain a much better agreement between the predictions of the creep recovery and the experimental data as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Predictions of $\varepsilon_2(t)$ under $\sigma_2 = cte$ from VE and VE-VP models compared to the experimental data.

INTERACTIONS BETWEEN LOADING MODES

In some problems we only have to consider static or quasi-static loading conditions. For other applications we may have no permanent loadings and we have only to consider the fatigue behaviour. Not only mechanical loadings may occur, but we can have applications with temperature changes and moisture uptake and diffusion.

If we are able to predict the responses to simple mechanical or environmental loadings we have also to analyse the possible interactions between those simple loading modes if a general complex loading is expected.

As early as 1970, J. Bax, [36] observed an acceleration of the creep evolution after a limited number of low frequency pressure oscillations on glass fibre reinforced polyester and epoxy filament-wound tubes under internal pressure with a possible reduction in life time of some 80%.

If we apply a limited number of cyclic loadings to the UD-reinforced Fibredux 920C-TS-5-42 specimen followed by the static loading we observe for high stress levels an acceleration of the creep behaviour and we have an important difference with the predictions obtained from the VE-VP model as shown in Fig. 2. This acceleration of the creep evolution is not observed at all loading levels. At lower stress levels the dynamic loading seems not to modify the creep behaviour. This acceleration is probably related to some damage induced by the dynamic loading and it is important to identify the limit loading levels safe for this combined loading effect.

Fig. 2. Comparison between the creep evolution in the transverse direction of a unidirectional reinforced composite without and with a first cyclic loading.

STRENGTH EVOLUTION – DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

If we have to predict the life time under a specific loading programme, or if we have to identify the maximum admissible loading levels for an imposed life time, or if we have to predict the residual structural integrity after an estimated time period, we have not only to consider the stiffness evolution but we have also to predict the time dependent strength evolution or the damage initiation and development.

This can be achieved on the basis of the assumption that the time-temperature-stress superposition principle can also be applied to the strength evolution as proposed by Y. Miyano [14-15-16].

It is also possible to apply a Tsai-Hill failure criterion (eq. 5) at the lamina level with time and temperature dependent strength characteristics followed by a ply-discount scheme as proposed by M. Tuttle, [37].

$$\frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{X^2(T)} - \frac{\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22}}{X^2(T)} + \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{[Y(t,T)]^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{[S(t,T)]^2} \geq 1 ; \quad (5)$$

with $X(T)$: temperature dependent strength in the fibre directions;
 $Y(t,T)$: time and temperature dependent strength in the transverse direction;
 $S(t,T)$: time and temperature dependent shear strength.

Y and S are assumed to have the following form :

$$Y(t,T) = A(T) - B(T) \log(t)$$

$$S(t,T) = C(T) - D(T) \log(t) .$$

A, B, C and D have to be obtained by creep to rupture tests. Cumulative damage has to be taken into account if ply stresses change with time and this may happen even if the external load remains constant due to the VE-VP behaviour.

This also corresponds to what we consider as local time dependent effects were the fibre stresses increase and the matrix stresses decrease as results of the relaxation effects. Those stress transfers are function of the interaction level between fibres and matrix. The amount of stress transfers can be measured by the moduli of imperfect interface conditions as introduced by J. Achenbach et al., [28].

When a lamina fails the stiffness is reduced following the classical ply discount scheme. It is also possible to consider an extension of our VE-VP model in order to include damage development. We consider damage as an irreversible rupture of the interactions at a certain level of the material scales. As consequence of those ruptures along a certain number of planes with orientations \bar{n} in a point no stress vectors can be built up and no stress transfers are possible for those orientations.

For the damage model to be added to our basic VE-VP model we can use a viscoplastic model with a yield stress element decreasing function of the number of cycles, of time, of environmental changes and of some internal time factors if we have to take into account ageing and/or degradation.

For this combined VE-VP damage prediction model we have as expression for the total strain

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_{ve} + \varepsilon_{vp} + \varepsilon_d, \quad (6)$$

$\varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_{ve}$ = given by the Schapery equations,

ε_{vp} = described by the Zapas-Crissman functional,

$\varepsilon_d = \Delta\lambda_d \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma}$, where f is a potential function as used in the plasticity theory.

We have to perform a number of failure tests in order to identify the significant damage parameters and the potential function. This damage component is similar to those proposed by V. Tamasz et al., [38].

EXPERIMENTAL DAMAGE CONTROL

For the identification of the damage parameters to be used in the damage component of our prediction model, there is a need of experimental information. Modulus degradation observed in the stress-strain curves and evolution of the residual permanent strain are damage indicators. Those informations obtained by cyclic loadings are easy to measure for elasto-plastic materials but it is much more time consuming to obtain them in the case of time-dependent materials.

A damage measure is only valid as long as the measurement technique is able to obtain strain values commensurate with the size of the inferred damage region or some representative volume element, (RVE).

One might question if the strain measured by an electrical strain gage is truly representative of the strain within the damaged region especially when the failure occurs outside of the strain measurement device range. Moduli obtained by these classical measurements might not be representative of the local constitutive behaviour and are not compatible with analytical models based upon global observations. One can show that under creep conditions, where the applied force remain constant, stresses are not uniform but vary over the whole test area due to imperfections and defects resulting from the curing process.

As consequence we have a non-homogeneous strain field and it will be essential to have an observation method that enables us to see the transformation of the homogeneous strain field to a heterogeneous one and to visualize the localisation effects, starting elements of failure initiation. For those observations full field methods are most interesting. Those methods include photoelastic analysis on photoelastic coatings, moiré analysis and stress pattern analysis by thermoelastic emission (SPATE). For some of those methods a surface preparation is needed or specific loading conditions have to be superimposed on the normal loading conditions.

ELECTRONIC SPECKLE PATTERN INTERFEROMETRY

The possibility to use the ESPI-technique for the observation of the localisation of the strain field during loading was discussed by P.J.P. Bouquet et al., [39].

The technology is based on the scattered reflection of incident light on a rough surface. In this case the surface of a test specimen which is illuminated with monochromatic laserlight. By applying laserlight the scattered light will have a characteristic granular appearance the so-called speckle pattern. Let us consider a rough surface illuminated by a laser beam. Each point from the reflection surface scatters the emitted wave. At any point on the observation plane the light field arises from the different points of the illuminated surface. The path lengths travelled by these waves, from source to object point to the receiving point, can differ from zero to multiples of wavelengths, depending on surface roughness and the geometry of the system. Interference of the dephased but coherent waves arriving at the receiving point will cause the resultant irradiance to be anything from dark to fully bright. The resultant of the waves arriving at a neighbouring point will probably give a quite different brightness. This variation in resultant irradiance from one receiving point to another is the cause of laser speckle. This type of speckle is known as the objective speckle.

When using two identical waves symmetrical incident on an object surface; a camera aligned perpendicular to the reflecting surface will visualise an interferential image due to the combination of the two speckle patterns.

Correlation fringes in ESPI are observed by a process of video signal subtraction or addition. The subtraction process is used in the Ettemeyer device (see Fig. 3). The camera video signal corresponding to the interferometer image plane speckle pattern of the undisplaced object is stored electronically, whereas the live video image of the displaced object, detected by the camera, is subtracted from the stored picture electronically. The output is then high-pass filtered, rectified and displayed on a monitor where the correlation fringes are observed in real time. In order to understand the formation of fringes, consider the intensities of the beams I_{before} , before displacement and I_{after} the intensity after displacement in each point of the image.

$$I_{\text{before}}(x, y) = I_R + I_0 + 2\sqrt{I_R I_0} \cos\phi \quad (7.1)$$

$$I_{\text{after}}(x, y) = I_R + I_0 + 2\sqrt{I_R I_0} \cos(\phi + \Delta\phi) \quad (7.2)$$

where ϕ is the phase difference between the reference beam and the object beam before the displacement, $\Delta\phi$ is the phase change caused by the displacement.

Assumed that the camera output signals V_{before} and V_{after} are proportional to the input image intensities, the subtracted signal V_s is then given by

$$V_s = (V_{\text{before}} - V_{\text{after}}) \propto (I_{\text{before}} - I_{\text{after}}) \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= 2\sqrt{I_R I_0} [\cos\phi - \cos(\phi + \Delta\phi)] \\ &= 4\sqrt{I_R I_0} \sin\left(\phi + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\phi\right) \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\Delta\phi\right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Negative and positive values are obtained from these equations, in which the negative-going signals are displayed as black areas.

Fig. 3. Set-up of the ESPI camera in a tensile test

CALIBRATION OF THE ESPI

In order to obtain valid quantitative results we have to calibrate the obtained images on the basis of another measurement system or a known pattern. Comparison with strain gage measurements on homogeneous strain fields gave us excellent agreement.

A central hole in a $[+/-45^\circ, 90^\circ_3]_S$ composite was monitored in order to evaluate the possibility to measure inhomogeneous strain development in the vicinity of the geometric non linearity. We obtain the displacement field for different loading steps as shown in Fig. 4.

Following further loading we see some noisy areas shown in Fig. 5.

The noisy areas, some appearing even in Fig. 4b, are very clear in Fig. 5. Those noisy areas appear to be the unstable strain regions on the surface of the beam where the rupture crack develops as shown on the image of the broken specimen, Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Image of the tensile loaded $[\pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ_3]_s$ specimen after rupture.

CRACK INITIATION DETECTION

We have used a $[90^\circ]_{10}$ laminate, carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (Fibredux 920 CX-TS-5-42) for the rupture test under ESPI-control with special attention to the out of plane displacements.

In the figures 7a, b, c the displacement fields are shown for higher stress levels

The inclined lines for the x and y displacements are due to the sensitivity of the optical equipment to the misalignment of the specimen in the testbench. With electrical strain gages this would be almost undetectable. In the z displacement the left border shows some deviation of the displacement field, green and red area.

The specimen was loaded up to 40.3 MPa.

For the x displacement no evidence of strain heterogeneity is observed (Fig. 8a).

In the y and z displacement images (Fig. 8b en 8c), localisation effects appear at the left border. The locus of those localisation images on the left border is also the place of initiation of the crack as can be observed on the overlay figure of the z displacement at 40.3 MPa with the broken specimen shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 : live image of the broken specimen with the analysed area in overlay

CONCLUSIONS – FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

On the basis of short-term creep and creep recovery tests, completed by fatigue tests and cyclic loadings at different constant and changing environmental conditions we are able to predict long term stiffness evolution by application of a NLVE-VP model. Short term failure analysis allows us to obtain the time and environment dependent strength characteristics, basis for the definition of admissible stress states corresponding to an imposed life time. Full field optical methods allows us to follow the localisation of the strain field, giving us a good indicator of the damage initiation, development and failure. Those optical informations give us the necessary elements for the definition of a damage component to be added to the basic NLVE-VP model so that we are able to predict residual structural integrity conditions for a construction under a combined mechanical and environmental loading history. We have to develop mixed numerical-experimental methods in order to arrive at the measure of an in volume event starting from the observation of a surface event. A better understanding of the ageing phenomena and degradation of matrix, fibre and interaction levels in between is a basic condition for more reliable structural applications of fibre reinforced polymer matrix composite construction components.

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